

Power Line Noise Effects and New Radio Noise Models

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Abstract

The EMC Technical Center (ECTC) conducted a three year radio noise measurement study at 30 HF communication sites operated by the US Navy, US Army, and US Air Force. This paper presents two new models which describe the median noise observed at these sites. The models closely describe the characteristics of noise at sites with noisy power lines and at sites with quiet power lines. Compared to the CCIR 258 noise models, the new models more accurately predict the impact of power line noise at HF communication sites. The new models can also be used to show the overall benefit of mitigating power line noise around HF communication sites.

Discussions

ECTC personnel used the RFI/EMI Automated Noise Measurement System (REAMS)¹ to collect noise data at both continental US and overseas HF radio communication sites operated by the US uniformed services. The data was taken over three years of measurements, beginning early 1989.

Radio noise models^{2,3} from CCIR-258 classify sites into four categories, namely Business, Residential, Rural, and Quiet Rural. These are empirical models based on measurements reported prior to 1978 and are defined by the equations below:

$$F_{AM} = -27.7 \log_{10} f_{MHz} + k_1 \quad (1)$$

where F_{AM} is in dB(kT0), k is the Boltzmann constant, T is room temperature in degrees Kelvin, $k_1 = 76.8$ for business, 72.5 for residential, and 67.2 for rural areas. The quiet rural area model is defined by:

$$F_{AM} = -28.6 \log_{10} f_{MHz} + 53.6 \quad (2)$$

Except for the rural category, the CCIR models did not closely describe our test data. After further analysis of the data and site layouts, we concluded that noise at these sites can be modeled as follows:

a. **Model for Sites with Noisy Power Lines.** Power line noise dominated the electromagnetic environment at most of the sites. For these sites, the services had no control over the proliferation of power distribution lines supplying power to the communities around the facilities. Most of the noise observed are gap discharge noise emanating from defective power distribution line components like broken insulators and burned out lightning arresters. A typical site is shown in Figure 1. Data and a linear curve fit of the median of the measurement medians for noisy sites are shown in Figure 2. The linear curve fit can be used as the new noise model and should be a proper estimate of noise resulting from power line EMI.

b. **Model for Sites with Quiet Power Lines.** - This model describes the noise at sites where there is only one power distribut-

Figure 1. Typical Site Layout.

Figure 2. Noise spectra at sites with noisy power lines.

Figure 3. Noise spectra at sites with quiet power lines.

ion line (10 kV to 66 kV) approaching the facilities with the last 600 meters underground (Fig 1), no appreciable power line noise sources within 5-10 kilometers, and other power lines skirt the site by at least 2 kilometers. At the antennas of these facilities, minimal or no AC power line EMI was observed.

In order to validate these new models, the ECTC intends to collect

Figure 4. Test data from four sites with underground power lines.

more data, starting at Columbia, Maryland. This city is unique as its zoning laws do not allow overhead AC power distribution lines. We collected noise data at the Kings Contrivance Shopping Center, the Columbia Mall, the Kings Contrivance Townhomes, and the Fulton Estates Village. The first two sites would meet the CCIR 258 "Business Areas" classification, while the last two sites could be classified as CCIR 258 "Residential Areas." Figure 4 compares the noise at the test sites to the model for sites with quiet power lines and the CCIR 258 noise models. The Columbia, MD test sites data deviated significantly from the CCIR business and residential area models. At the same time, the Columbia test data are very close to both the CCIR rural and the new "quiet site" model.

The site noise standard deviation from the measurements in this paper are about 2 to 3.5 dB less than the CCIR 258 "Rural Area" standard deviation. Figure 5 shows the standard deviation extracted from the ECTC study median amplitude probability distribution curves. The standard deviations for noisy sites and

Figure 5. Standard deviation from measurement APD curves.

quiet sites can be described by Equations 3 and 4 below.

$$S_d = -0.43 \log_{10}(f_{MHz}) + 5.66 \quad \text{in dB (3)}$$

$$S_d = -0.24 \log_{10}(f_{MHz}) + 4.86 \quad \text{in dB (4)}$$

Applications

The models shown in figures 2, 3, and 4 can be used to describe the HF radio noise found at radio communication sites. When there are one or more gap noise or corona noise sources within 10 kilometers of the site and there are power distribution lines other than the feeder lines closer than two kilometers to the site, then the noisy site model in Figure 2 (Eq 5) can be used.

$$F_{AM} = -37.5 \log_{10}(f_{MHz}) + 83.2 \quad (5)$$

When the only power distribution line around the site is the site feeder line and there are no gap noise and no corona noise sources within line of sight, then we can use the model Figure 3 (Eq 6).

$$F_{AM} = -29.1 \log_{10}(f_{MHz}) + 65.2 \quad (6)$$

The new noise models are useful in estimating possible improvements mitigating power line noise around existing communication sites. For example, the signal to noise improvement from eliminating power line noise around a site can be calculated directly by subtracting Equation 6 from Equation 5. At 3 Mhz, the improvement will be approximately 13.99 dB.

Conclusion

The models for sites with "Noisy Power Lines" and "Quiet Power Lines" have been validated from 500 kHz to 30 MHz and can be used in addition to the CCIR 258 noise models to describe electromagnetic noise at HF communication sites.

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References

1. V. P. Arafiles and L. L. Turner, " RFI/EMI Automated Measurement System (REAMS)," 1991 IEEE International Symposium on EMC Record, IEEE, NY, pp 448-451, August 1991.
2. CCIR, "Man-Made Radio Noise," Report 258-3, International Radio Consultative Committee (CCIR), ITU, Geneva, Switzerland, 1978.
3. ANSI/IEEE Std 473-1985, IEEE Recommended Practice for an Electromagnetic Site Survey (10 kHz to 10 GHz), IEEE, NY, pp 13-14, June 18, 1985.